

From the end of March to April, the bugs were few, but from May to July severe outbreaks were noticed in some fields. The trials with fertilizer, date of seeding, and *cropping system* were heavily infested. The severely infested varieties were Durga (IET2938) and Laxmi (IR206I-628-1-61-3). The mealybug infestation in the plots of the cropping systems trial ranged from 42.5% to 72.5% infested hills. Each plot had 1,250 hill. The outbreak may have been due to drought during May-July 1980.

Because of the insect's economic importance, an experiment determined possible alternate hosts by artificial inoculation. The common weeds of rice fields and sugarcane were planted in pots. Some nymphs of the rice mealybugs were inoculated into the leaf sheaths and kept for multiplication in the glasshouse. Sugarcane is attacked by the mealybug *Saccharicoccus sacchari*,

Alternate hosts of rice mealybug. Nepal, 1980.

Host	Infested parts	
	Summer	Winter
<i>Saccharum officinarum</i>	Leaf sheath	Inside old leaf sheath
<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i>		Inflorescence + leaf sheath
<i>Echinochloa colonum</i>		
<i>Cyperus difformis</i>	Floral parts + leaf sheath	Floral part
<i>Cyperus rotundus</i>		
<i>Cyperus iria</i>		
<i>Cynodon dactylon</i>	Leaf sheath	Leaf sheath
<i>Phalans minor</i>	Leaf sheath + panicle	Leaf sheath + panicle
<i>Fimbristylis littoralis</i>	Leaf sheath	Leaf sheath
<i>Leptochloa chinensis</i>		
<i>Setaria</i> sp.	Inflorescence + leaf sheath	Inflorescence + leaf sheath
<i>Eleusine</i> sp.		
Some unidentified grasses	Leaf sheath	Leaf sheath

but *Brevinnia rehi* is the species that usually occurs in the rice fields. The nymphs inoculated into the sugarcane were observed only in the basal part during the early experimental period, but later the bugs were observed sucking and multiplying. The multiplication pattern shows that sugarcane is a more

suitable host than is the rice plant itself. Overwintering nymphs and adults were also observed in the experiment, but the multiplication rate is slow during off-season in the alternate host plants in both field and glasshouse. The alternate host plants, their infested parts, and infestation periods are in the table. ■

Insect pests on *Azolla pinnata* at Bangkhen, Thailand

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Insects were observed attacking *Azolla pinnata* R. Br. in ponds at Bangkhen, Thailand, during Sep-Nov 1977. Five species were collected: two Lepidoptera: Pyralidae — *Cryptoblades* sp. near *gnidiella* Milliere (det. by M. Shaffer, British Museum, London, Eng.) and *Nymphula enixalis* (det. by E. G. Munroe, Agr. Canada Research Branch, Ottawa, Canada); Diptera: Chironomidae — *Polypedilum johannseni* Sublette and Sublette (det. by J. Sublette, Eastern New Mexico Univ., Portales, N. M., USA); Coleoptera: Curculionidae — *Bagous* sp. near *nodieri* Hustache (det. by E. C. Zimmerman, CSIRO, Canberra, Australia); Orthoptera: Tettigidae — *Criotettix* sp. (det. by L. Pitkin, British Museum).

Feeding damage in some ponds was severe. *Criotettix* sp. (see photo) was the most destructive. It also consumed *Lemna minor* L. and *Pistia stratiotes* L. *Cryptoblades* sp. was very important, despite heavy ant predation and parasitism by an unidentified braconid wasp.

Four pests of azolla from Bangkhen, Thailand. A. *Criotettix* sp. (2-cm body length), B. *Nymphula enixalis* (1.6-cm wing span).

C-*Cryptoblabes* sp. (1.2-cm wing span),
D-*Bagous* sp. (2-mm body length).

N. enixalis caused significant damage. *P. johannseni* may be important because of its high numbers, but assessment was difficult since it appeared primarily detritivorous, feeding facultatively on azolla. *Bagous* sp. was a minor pest.

Weekly samples were taken from a 280-m² pond at the Kasetsart University campus October 1977. Pond coverage by azolla declined from 100% to 1% during sampling. Samples were taken only from sections with dense, uniform plant growth. A 100-cm² net, with 11.3-cm mouth diameter, mounted on a bamboo pole, was slowly lifted from beneath the water surface to gather plants. Insects were separated by vigorous shaking in a

Relative abundance of 4 insect pests of *Azolla pinnata*, Bangkhen, Thailand, 11-27 October 1977.

Date	Samples (no.)	No./100 cm ^{2a}			
		<i>Crymhlubes</i>	<i>Nymphula</i>	<i>Polypedilum</i>	<i>Bagous</i>
11 Oct	27	0.41 ± 1.01	0.26 ± 0.53	36.78 ± 40.87	0
17 Oct	24	1.71 ± 3.62	0.38 ± 0.92	186.92 ± 153.07	0.25 ± 0.85
24 Oct	3	0.67 ± 1.15	0.33 ± 0.58	54.67 ± 29.57	0
27 Oct	1	0	0	37	0

^a± = standard deviation.

0.05% detergent solution. Because azolla coverage progressively declined, the number of netfuls taken each week was reduced to maintain an approximately 1-1,000 ratio between the plant area represented in the sample and the pond area covered by azolla.

Of the four species sampled, *P.*

johannseni was most abundant and *Bagous* sp. the least (see table). *Criotetrix* sp. was present on all dates, averaging 2-4/100 cm². It did not appear in the samples because it escaped capture. Although azolla decline generally correlated with insect density, the exact cause is unknown. ■

Biochemical basis of insecticide-induced brown planthopper resurgence

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Application of certain insecticides on brown planthopper (BPH)-susceptible rices is known to induce resurgence of BPH populations both in the greenhouse and in the field. This has been attributed primarily to increased BPH feeding and reproductive rates, reduced nymphal periods, enhanced adult life, and killing of predators. We investigated the biochemical changes that take place in the rice plant after insecticide applica-

tions because pest resurgence is believed to be at least partially a host plant-mediated phenomenon. We found that when plants of the BPH-susceptible Taichung Native 1 (TN1) were sprayed

with decamethrin, a strong resurgence-causing insecticide, levels of free amino nitrogen in the leaf sheath were significantly higher than in TN1 plants sprayed with Perthane, a nonresurgence

Carbohydrate and nitrogen levels in leaf sheaths of insecticide-treated rice plants. IRRI, 1980.^a

Variety	Treatment	Starch (%)	Soluble sugars (%)	Nitrogen (%)	Carbohydrate-nitrogen ratio	Free amino nitrogen (mg leucine/g sample)
TN1	Methyl parathion	5.97 a	1.67 a	1.77 ab	0.94	1.15 ab
	Decamethrin	6.65 a	1.02 a	1.88 a	0.54	1.34 a
	Perthane	4.70 a	1.44 a	1.57 b	0.92	0.76 b
	Water (control)	4.40 a	1.80 a	1.90 a	0.95	1.06 ab
IR36	Methyl parathion	7.02 a	1.85 a	1.63 b	1.13	0.75 b
	Decamethrin	7.32 a	1.06 a	1.55 b	0.68	0.98 ab
	Perthane	7.32 a	1.58 a	1.57 b	1.01	0.75 b
	Water (control)	8.81 a	1.47 a	1.58 b	0.93	0.92 ab

^aChemical analysis according to *Laboratory Manual for Physiological Studies of Rice* (Yoshida et al 1972) and *Cereal Chemistry Procedures* (Juliano 1974), IRRI. Means of 2 replications. Means within a column followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.